

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CORONARY ARTERIES' STENOSIS ON THE RESULTS OF CORONARY ANGIOGRAPHY AND THE AGATSTON INDEX IN PATIENTS WITH CORONARY HEART DISEASE AND DIABETES MELLITUS

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Relevance. Coronary artery disease (CAD) and type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM) are common and frequently co-occurring diseases. There is a clear link between diabetes and cardiovascular disease (CVD). CVD, and specifically cardiovascular outcomes, are the main cause of death in patients with diabetes in both men and women [1].

Purpose of the research: to compare the level of coronary arteries' (CA) stenosis according to coronary angiography (CAG) and coronary calcium (CC) according to the results of multislice computed tomography (MSCT) of the heart in patients with CAD with and without DM.

Research methods. The study was conducted at the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center for Cardiology. The study involved 90 people (43 women, 47 men) aged 45-70 years. All patients underwent MSCT with the determination of CC and CAG. The patients were divided into two groups: a group of patients with CAD and DM (45 people) and a group of patients with CAD without DM (45 people).

Research results. The CC index is calculated on the images as the sum of the area of calcium inclusions with a density above 130 Hounsfield units (HU) multiplied by the density factor. The density factor depends on the maximum density index in the area of interest: factor 1 130-199 HU, factor 2 - 200-299 HU, factor 3 - 300-399 HU, factor 4 >400 HU. Gradation of coronary artery lesions according to the Agaston index: 0 - no signs of injury (group A); 1-10 - minimal lesions (group B); 11-100 - minor lesions (group C); 101-400 - moderate lesion (Group D); more than 400 - severe defeat (group E). Of the studied patients in group 1, 4 (8,8%) were included in group B; 16 (35,6%) were included in group C, CAG revealed hemodynamically insignificant stenosis of the coronary artery; 23 (51,1%) were included in group D, with CAG in 17 patients - 50-60% stenosis of the coronary artery and in 6 - more than 70% stenosis of the coronary artery; 2 (4,5%) patients were included in the D group, with more than 70% coronary artery stenosis in CAG. 8 patients underwent angioplasty with coronary artery stenting[2]. In group 2, in patients with CHD and DM, 3 (6.7%) patients were included in group B, 5 (11.1%) in group C (with CAH, stenosis was 35+5.5%), 26 (57.8%)) were included in group D: stenosis was 50-60% in 15 patients, more than 70% in 11 patients; 11 (24.4%) patients were included in group D, with CAG revealed stenosis of more than 70%. 20 patients underwent angioplasty with coronary artery stenting, 2 patients were offered aortocoronary bypass grafting (ACBG)[3].

Conclusion: A direct correlation was found between the level of coronary artery stenosis according to CAG data and the Agatston index both in patients with and without DM. In the group with DM 2, patients were offered ACBG, while in group 1 there were no such patients.

Due to the ease of implementation, cost-effectiveness and practically no contraindications, the definition of CC has become widespread, especially during screening in patients with suspected coronary heart disease.

References:

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